

SHORELINE DYNAMICS AND COASTAL MANAGEMENT ALONG THE EASTERN COAST OF LAGOS, NIGERIA: SUCCESSFUL, BUT SUSTAINABLE?

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Abstract

This study investigates the evolution of the Lagos shoreline using satellite imagery and geospatial datasets obtained from the Digital Earth Africa (DEA) platform. Groynes, intended to mitigate longshore sediment transport, have successfully facilitated accretion within protected segments but have also exacerbated erosion in adjacent unprotected areas. Shoreline retreats of 248.28 m, 116.24 m, and 245.42 m were documented before the first groyne, between the first and second groynes, and beyond the last groyne, respectively, between the years 2000 and 2022. An average erosion rate of -0.13 m/yr was recorded prior to 2015 and -13.80 m/yr after 2015 at the segment before the first groyne. Between the first and second groynes, an average erosion rate of -3.20 m/yr was recorded prior to 2015 and -0.09 m/yr after 2015. Immediately following the last groyne, the subsequent segment recorded accretion at an average rate of +0.32 m/yr prior to 2015 and a concerning average erosion rate of -28.10 m/yr. Atican Beach recorded an average erosion rate of -0.07 m/yr prior to 2015 and an average accretion rate of +0.22 m/yr after 2015. The alternating patterns of erosion and accretion observed prior to 2015 were supplanted by more pronounced erosion in subsequent years, reflecting the cumulative effects of groyne construction, rising sea levels, and anthropogenic pressures. These findings underscore the necessity of integrated coastal zone management strategies that combine hard engineering solutions with soft approaches, continuous monitoring, environmental regulations, and community engagement to achieve long-term shoreline stability. The paper concludes that the Lekki coastline provides valuable insights for coastal managers and policymakers, highlighting the importance of anticipating and mitigating the secondary effects of protective structures to ensure the resilience of vulnerable coastal areas in the face of ongoing environmental changes.

Keywords: Erosion, Accretion, Groynes, Shoreline, Satellite imagery, Coastal zone management

1.0 Introduction

Coastal erosion is a global environmental challenge that affects millions of people living along the world's coastlines. It is driven by both natural forces such as wave action, sea-level rise, and storms, as well as anthropogenic activities including sand mining, infrastructure development, and deforestation of coastal buffers (Esteves, 2014; Luijendijk *et al.*, 2018). Shoreline retreat not

only leads to the loss of land and habitats but also threatens coastal economies, infrastructure, and human settlements. The growing impact of climate change, particularly rising sea levels and increased storm intensities, has further exacerbated the rate and severity of coastal erosion across various regions of the world, especially in low-lying coastal zones.

In Africa, coastal erosion has become an acute problem, especially in densely populated urban and peri-urban areas. West African countries, including Ghana, Côte d'Ivoire, Senegal, and Nigeria, have experienced alarming shoreline retreats—sometimes exceeding 10 meters annually (World Bank, 2019). Poor land-use planning, unregulated sand mining and rapid urban development without adequate coastal protection measures have been major contributors. Efforts to mitigate erosion in Africa often rely on hard-engineering interventions such as groynes, seawalls, and breakwaters; however, these solutions sometimes cause further degradation in downdrift areas due to disruption of natural sediment transport (Njue *et al.*, 2021).

In Nigeria, the eastern section of the Lagos coastal zone has undergone significant and accelerated coastal erosion over the past two decades, primarily driven by both natural dynamics and human activities. Critical areas such as Bar Beach, Kuramo Waters, and the Lekki Peninsula have recorded shoreline retreats of several meters annually, endangering infrastructure, ecosystems, and livelihoods (Olabode *et al.*, 2020a; Olabode *et al.*, 2020b; Akinluyi *et al.*, 2022). To address persistent erosion and flooding threats in Victoria Island, the Eko Atlantic City Project was launched in the early 2000s. This large-scale reclamation project sought to protect the city through the construction of massive rock revetments known as the Great Wall of Lagos (Adeloye and Ayolabi, 2018). While this effort has safeguarded Victoria Island, it has also altered sediment dynamics, affecting erosion patterns along the downdrift eastern coast. As a further measure, groynes were installed between 2010 and 2015 along the Lekki shoreline to trap sediments and stabilize the beach (Ogunbayo and Bankole, 2021). Since 2015, the area has faced growing anthropogenic pressures, including rapid urban expansion, deforestation of coastal vegetation, unregulated sand mining, and proliferation of informal settlements and tourism infrastructure (Adelekan, 2020; Elias and Oyebande, 2021; Akintola *et al.*, 2019). These activities have disrupted natural sediment transport, increased surface runoff, and heightened the vulnerability of the coastline to erosion and storm surges. Consequently, reclamation efforts such as Eko Atlantic have inadvertently contributed to terminal erosion in adjacent, unprotected zones (Olowu *et al.*, 2022). The objectives of the paper are to examine the spatial and temporal evolution of shoreline changes between 2000 and 2022, and to assess the impacts of engineering structures—specifically groynes—on shoreline stability along the Eastern Lagos coast.

2.0 Methodology

Study Area

Lagos, situated in the southwestern part of Nigeria along Africa's West Coast, functions as one of the major commercial centres in the country. Geologically, it lies within the coastal sedimentary basin of the Dahomey Embayment, which extends from southeastern Ghana through Togo and Benin into southwestern Nigeria. The geology of Lagos is largely defined by Quaternary to recent sedimentary formations, consisting primarily of unconsolidated coastal sands, silts, clay, and peat deposits (Adepelumi *et al.*, 2008). The Gulf of Guinea lies to its south, while the Okitipupa Ridge is to the east (Omatshola and Adegoke, 1981). The harbour in Lagos, depicted in Figure 1, is Nigeria's most crucial seaport and the first entry point from the Atlantic Ocean, beyond the Republic of Benin (Balogun and Ladigbolu 2011). It forms one of the three main parts of the Lagos Lagoon Complex, with the other parts being the Metropolitan and Epe Division Segments.

The harbour is 2 km wide and receives water from Lagos Lagoon to the north and Badagry Creek to the west. Oil depots are located along the western shores, while urban and industrial developments are found on the eastern shores. This study focuses on the Eastern Lagos Coastal zone in Lagos State, Nigeria (Figure 1), which is highly vulnerable to erosion, flooding, and rising sea levels. This area was chosen due to its noticeable shoreline erosion, infrastructure risks, and socioeconomic importance.

Figure 1: Location of the Study area

Data Sources

Shoreline change analysis was conducted exclusively utilizing geospatial datasets obtained from the Digital Earth Africa (DEA) platform, which employs satellite imagery, including Landsat and Sentinel datasets, to automate coastline products. The DEA coastline datasets, known for their temporal consistency and high quality, served as the primary data source for this study. Shoreline datasets from the years 2000 and 2022 were accessed directly via the DEA map platform. All analyses were based on pre-processed atmospherically corrected surface reflectance datasets. The analysis commenced with the retrieval of available shoreline data layers corresponding to each target year. These datasets facilitated the generation of visual representations of shoreline positions, enabling the identification of areas of erosion and accretion. The DEA shoreline was delineated using an automated algorithm, providing a reliable baseline for temporal comparisons within the study area. To enhance the spatial interpretation of shoreline dynamics, shoreline positions from different years were visually overlaid using the DEA platform and cross-verified with high-resolution imagery (SPOT) and historical Google Earth snapshots, which were employed to validate the accuracy of the delineated automated shoreline. Changes in shoreline position over time were assessed by comparing shoreline features from sequential years. DEA

platform tools were utilized to measure the landward and seaward movement of the shoreline by calculating the linear displacement between shorelines at different positions. These measurements yielded data on the extent of shoreline retreat and advance for each segment of the coastline. The spatial extent of the changes was quantified by measuring the area of land loss and gain, derived from the digital shoreline positions and the associated polygons generated from the DEA platform. To quantify shoreline changes during the study period, the overlaid shoreline position was used to delineate polygons representing areas of landward retreat and seaward advance. The DEA built-in measurement tools were employed to compute the total area of the polygons directly, expressed in square kilometres. The percentage of land loss and gain was calculated relative to the initial shoreline position for each year of the study. The rate of change was determined by dividing the extent of the shoreline measurement by the duration of the respective year, which was expressed in meters per year. The analysis was validated by cross-referencing the digital Earth Africa-derived shoreline position with high-resolution historical Google Earth imagery and local survey data to ensure the robustness of the study. The map was embellished using ArcGIS 10.4 version and Excel for erosion and accretion trends, see Figures 2 and 3.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of processes Fig. 3: Graphical representation of study area

3.0 Results

Evolution of the Eastern Lagos Coastal Zone (2000-2014) pre-gryones era

Between 2000 and 2014, the Eastern Lagos coastal zone (Figure 4) experienced significant evolution driven by a combination of natural coastal dynamics, anthropogenic interventions, and climate change impacts. This period marked a transition from largely natural shoreline behaviour to a heavily modified coastal landscape, reflecting global coastal urbanization trends. From satellite-based observations and Digital Earth Africa data, the eastern Lagos shoreline—particularly between Bar Beach, Lekki, and Atican Beach—underwent measurable

Figure 4: Part of the Eastern axis of Lagos Coastal zone showing Atlantic City, Gryones position and Atican beach. Source: Google earth image assessed 20/3/25

erosion and accretion cycles (Figure 4 and Table 1). The period from 2000 to approximately 2014 was characterized by unregulated coastal retreat. This erosion was primarily driven by longshore drift, wave action, and the lack of protective infrastructure. During this period the installation of the groynes was in progress.

At the segment before the location of the first groyne (Figure 5), there was gradual and sustained erosion over the 14-year period. The shoreline retreated from 211.52m in 2000 to 119.72 m in 2014; resulting in a net shoreline seaward movement of -91.8 m. significant shoreline loss occurred between 2006-2008 and 2008-2011 of -55.41 m and -34.86 m respectively. In general, net erosion rate of -0.117 m was recorded at this segment. At the region between the location of the first and the second groyne (Figure 6) recorded the most severe and continuous erosion. The shoreline retreated from 93.04 m in 2000 to an alarming 2.21 m in 2014, a dramatic loss of -90.83 m. Significant shoreline loss occurred between 2006-2008 and 2009-2012 of -36.01 m and -28.98 m respectively. This segment recorded net erosion of -3.499 m. In contrast, the shoreline at the segment of the position after the groynes (Figure 7) remained relatively stable throughout the 14 years. It fluctuated modestly from 260.55 m in 2000 to 244.2 m in 2014, amounting to a retreat in shoreline of -16.35 m. It recorded a net accretion of +0.34 m. Atican beach (downdrift area) exhibited irregular but generally erosional behavior from 40.41 m in 2000; the shoreline retreated to 4.3 m by 2014, a total loss of -36.11 m. Although a temporary accretion of +8.11 m was recorded in 2014. It recorded a net retreat of -0.76 m.

Table 1: Shoreline change rate per m/yr

Year	Before first Groyne		Between first and second groyne		After the Groyne		Atican beach	
	Shoreline (m)	Er	Shoreline (m)	Erosion -/accretio n+ (m/yr)	Shoreline (m)	Erosion -/accretio n+ (m/yr)	Shoreline (m)	Erosion -/accretio n+ (m/yr)
2000	211.52	0	93.04	0	260.55	0	40.41	0
2001	207.51	-4.01	89.39	-3.65	263.4	2.85	41.36	0.95
2002		-0.54	88.51	88	262.38	-1.02	35.35	-6.01
2003	207.51	0.54	82.9	-5.61	258.38	-4	29.3	-6.05
2004	207.51	0	82.54	-0.36	259.82	1.44	29.46	0.16
2005	207.51	0	79.76	-2.78	264.5	4.68	32.43	2.97
2006	208.6	1.09	70.52	-9.24	NA	-	35.1	2.67
2007	NA	NA	NA	-	NA	-	NA	-
2008	153.19	-	34.51	-	243.99	NA	9.74	0
2009	153.19	0	34.51	0	241.78	-2.21	9.17	-0.57
2010	NA	-	NA	-	241.69	-0.09	9.11	-0.06
2011	118.33	-	18.18	-	241.44	-0.25	7.94	-1.17
2012	116.86	-1.47	5.53	-12.65	242.09	0.65	3.66	-4.28
2013	117.27	0.41	4.52	-1.01	243.56	1.47	-3.81	-7.47
2014	119.72	2.45	2.21	-2.31	244.2	0.64	4.3	8.11

2015	99.1	-20.62	4.21	2	235.29	-8.91	11.98	7.68
2016	67.3	-31.8		0.98	207.63	-27.66	16.04	4.06
2017	58.1	-9.2	1.11	-4.08	197.44	-10.19	17.29	1.25
2018	13.23	-44.87	3.57	2.46	105.31	-92.13	15.51	-1.78
2019	-0.29	13.52	-3.09	-6.66	75.9	-29.41	10.4	-5.11
2020	2.7	-2.99	-1.55	1.54	39	-36.9	10.77	0.37
2021	2.56	-0.14	-2.47	-0.92	30.33	-8.67	2.75	-8.02
2022	2.27	-0.29	1.53	4	18.83	-11.5	6.08	3.33

Figure. 5: Shoreline movement from Atlantic City towards the west of the first groyne

Figure 6: Shoreline movement within the segment between the first and the second groyne

Figure 7: Shoreline movement between the last groyne and Atican beach

Evolution of the Eastern Lagos Coastal Zone (2015-2022) post-gryones era

Analysis of shoreline changes from 2015 to 2022 shows significant spatial and temporal variation in erosion and accretion patterns across the eastern Lagos Coastal zone (Figure 8). Before the first gryone, there was a drastic retreat in shoreline position from 99.1 m in 2015 to 2.27 m in 2022, indicating erosion totalling approximately -96.83 m over the period. The most intense annual erosion occurred between 2017 and 2018 (-44.87 m). The net erosion rate at this segment is -12 m. Between the first and the second gryone, shoreline movement values fluctuate, with an initial minor accretion in 2015 (+2 m), followed by alternating erosion and limited accretion. This segment was unstable, ending in slight recovery in 2022 (+1.53 m accretion), yet still showing net erosion of -0.085 m. After the gryones, the shoreline declined steeply from 235.29 m in 2015 to 18.83 m in 2022, representing a cumulative erosion of -216.46 m, with the most severe shoreline retreat occurring between 2017 and 2018 (-92.13 m) Figure 8. The segment after the gryones has a net erosion rate of -28.17 m. At Atican Beach (downdrift side), the shoreline showed more resilience. After some accretion between 2015 and 2017, values fluctuated but remained relatively stable, dropping to 6.08 m by 2022. Despite temporary erosion phases for example -8.02 m in 2021, the overall change from 2015 to 2022 was comparatively moderate with a net accretion value of +0.22 m.

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Figure 8: Shoreline movement (m)

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4.0 Discussions

The examination of satellite imagery and coastline data from the Digital Earth Africa Map platform has identified substantial alterations in the shoreline along the eastern axis of Lagos between 2000 and 2022. In response to the ongoing coastal erosion along the Lekki shoreline in Lagos, Nigeria, a series of groynes were implemented as part of coastal defense strategies. These groynes, which are elongated, narrow structures constructed perpendicular to the shoreline, are designed to capture sand transported by longshore drift, thereby stabilizing the beach and mitigating the rate of erosion. The Lekki coastline has been particularly susceptible to erosion due to both natural and anthropogenic factors, including rising sea levels, unregulated coastal development, and intense wave energy from the Atlantic Ocean.

To address these challenges, groynes were primarily constructed in the eastern part of Lekki, extending from Alpha Beach towards Atican Beach. The initial set of groynes were constructed around 2010 under the Lagos State Government's Eko Atlantic protection initiative (Adesanya and Akinyemi, 2019) and finalized in 2015. Each groyne is engineered to extend several meters into the ocean, utilizing large boulders and reinforced concrete. Their spacing (approximately 0.35 km) and length (approximately 153.82 m) are strategically designed to promote sediment accumulation on the updrift side while minimizing erosion on the downdrift side (Faluyi and Adepelumi, 2020). The total width of the area covered by groynes is 7.25 km. The groynes are approximately a distance of 4 km from Atlantic City.

Immediately from the Atlantic City through a distance of approximately 647m, the shoreline is experiencing retreat and through a distance of 1.81km from the location, the shoreline is experiencing accretion and the remaining segment to the location of the groynes is experiencing erosion. Consequently, significant accretion has been observed in certain segments of the coastline, particularly between groynes, although some downdrift areas continue to experience sediment depletion and erosion, such as near Atican Beach. Recent shoreline monitoring data from 2000 to 2022 indicate that approximately 4 km length segment investigated in this study (Atlantic City to the first groyne) has experienced a shoreline retreat of -248.28 m over the study period. The segment between the first and second groynes experienced a landward shift of -116.24 m. The segment between the last groyne and Atican Beach, approximately 6.7 km apart, experienced a negative shoreline shift of -245.42 km from the year 2000 to 2022.

Erosion and accretion along the eastern coastline of Lagos varied over time, alternating between periods of sediment loss and gain, though not in equal measure, until around 2015. From that point, areas located before the first groyne and immediately after the last groyne experienced an increase in erosion rates. In contrast, the sections directly protected by the groynes, as well as the areas further east beyond the final groyne (such as Atican Beach), maintained a relatively balanced pattern of erosion and accretion. The findings indicate that while groyne-protected areas

show minor accretion, segments located before the first groyne and beyond the last groyne, particularly towards Atican Beach, continue to experience substantial erosion. This pattern aligns with observations from other global coasts where groyne construction, while locally effective, often leads to unintended downdrift erosion. For instance, studies along the New Jersey coast in the United States have shown that while groynes promote sediment accumulation on their updrift side, they exacerbate erosion on the downdrift side owing to sediment starvation (Nordstrom, 2014).

Similarly, along the Ghanaian coast, the installation of groynes at Ada led to pronounced beach buildup immediately adjacent to the structures but caused accelerated erosion further east (Boateng, 2012). In the eastern coastline of Lagos, the alternating pattern of erosion and accretion observed before 2015 was disrupted post-2015, with erosion becoming more dominant in the unprotected areas. Groynes has generally succeeded in stabilizing sections of the Lekki coastline between Alpha Beach and Atican Beach, but has also shifted the problem further along the coast. This phenomenon, often termed "terminal scour," is well documented; when the last groyne in a series is reached, the absence of further sediment-trapping structures results in intensified erosion beyond the final groyne (Dean and Dalrymple, 2002). Comparatively, in South Africa, groynes installed at Durban were similarly effective in beach stabilization within protected zones, but exacerbated erosion in unprotected adjacent areas, necessitating supplementary measures, such as sand nourishment programs (Mather, 2008).

Necessity for integrated Coastal Zone management approaches

The Lagos case shows a parallel need for integrated coastal zone management approaches that combine hard structures with soft engineering techniques, such as beach nourishment or dune stabilization. Moreover, anthropogenic activities, such as unregulated coastal developments, sand mining, and infrastructure expansion, have compounded the natural challenges posed by wave energy and sea level rise along the Lagos coastline (Obi, 2020; Nwilo et al., 2021). These factors must be considered in future coastal protection plans to avoid merely transferring erosion along the coast.

5.0 Conclusions

The analysis of shoreline change along the eastern coast of Lagos between 2000 and 2022 revealed a dynamic and evolving coastal system shaped by both natural forces and human interventions. The construction of groynes along the Lekki coastline has had a significant impact on stabilizing the shoreline within the protected segments, effectively promoting sediment accretion and mitigating localized erosion. However, these structures have also contributed to intensified erosion in adjacent unprotected areas, particularly before the first groyne and beyond the last groyne towards Atican Beach.

The results mirror the patterns observed in other parts of the world, where groyne installations, while initially effective, often lead to unintended downdrift erosion, emphasizing the complex and interconnected nature of coastal processes. The shoreline movements recorded — -248.28 m meters landward shift before the first groyne, -116.24 m between the first and second groynes, and -245.42 meters beyond the last groyne — underscore the need for holistic and adaptive coastal management strategies.

Additionally, the alternating patterns of erosion and accretion observed prior to 2015 were replaced by more pronounced erosion in the latter years, reflecting the cumulative effects of

groyne construction, rising sea levels, and anthropogenic pressures, such as sand mining and coastal development. These findings highlight the importance of not relying solely on hard engineering solutions, but combining them with soft engineering approaches, continuous monitoring, environmental regulations, and community engagement to achieve long-term shoreline stability.

Ultimately, experience with the Lekki coastline offers valuable lessons for coastal managers and policymakers. Future interventions should prioritize integrated and sustainable coastal zone management to anticipate and mitigate the secondary effects of protective structures. Only through a balanced approach that respects both natural dynamics and human needs can the resilience of vulnerable coastal areas such as Lekki be secured in the face of ongoing environmental change.

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4th African Institute for Science Policy and Innovation Biennial International Conference Proceedings

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